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Preface

Welcome to the book of extended abstracts for MARESEC 2026.

The 6th European Workshop on Maritime Systems Resilience and Security (MARESEC 2026) addressed research on resilience, security, and technology, including their ethical, legal, and social dimensions in the maritime domain. Topics included offshore and onshore infrastructure, navigation and shipping, as well as autonomous and sensing systems for maritime safety and security. The workshop aimed to bring together researchers to present new results and ongoing projects, exchange experiences, and explore possible collaborations.

This document includes all accepted extended abstracts for the workshop, sorted by session topic. All accepted contributions that were submitted as full papers have been published individually on Zenodo and can be found at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/maresec2026/records>

We would like to thank all authors and reviewers for their valuable contributions and efforts.

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Resilience & Security

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Design and Modelling of an Arctic Tabletop Exercise for Maritime Systems Resilience

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Keywords— *maritime, resilience, Arctic, tabletop, vulnerability, disruption, electricity, crisis, power system, PyPSA, modelling.*

The rapid militarisation of the High-North, the proliferation of hybrid threats and the accelerating impacts of climate change have turned the Arctic into a strategic vulnerability corridor for Europe's energy security. Norway occupies a pivotal position within this landscape, supplying approximately 31% of the European Union's gas imports and ranking as the EU's third-largest electricity trading partner. Any significant disruption to Arctic critical infrastructure would carry cascading consequences for European energy markets, environmental integrity, and human welfare — underscoring the urgent need for robust, evidence-based resilience frameworks.

To address these emerging risks, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, together with NATO's Energy Security Centre of Excellence (NATO ENSEC COE), the Naval Post-Graduate School (NPS) and the Ted Stevens Center for Arctic Security Studies (TSC), organised the Tabletop Exercise Coherent Resilience 2025 – Arctic (CORE 25-A), which took place in Sweden from 3 to 7 November 2025. The exercise convened over 120 participants from 21 nations and 56 organisations (including coast guards, ministries of defence, energy, police, EU and NATO bodies) to stress-test the collective resilience of critical maritime energy installations and distribution networks against hybrid threats and severe weather events. The exercise objectives covered four domains: critical energy infrastructure response, crisis management coordination, strategic communication, and the regulatory maritime framework.

The exercise unfolded across three distinct vignettes, depicting crisis scenarios of low, medium, and high intensity risk. Each vignette comprised a sequence of incidents (injects), with a total of 18 injects, triggering decision points that required coordination across organisational and functional boundaries.

To complement the qualitative insights derived from the exercise, a modelling work was conducted, using the open-source Python for Power System Analysis (PyPSA) software tool. PyPSA is an open-source toolbox designed for simulating and optimizing modern energy systems [1]. It excels at handling a mix of conventional generators, variable renewable energy sources (wind and solar), storage units, and transmission networks, allowing high spatial and temporal resolution. PyPSA is widely used in the industry and academia, by actors such as European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity, Joint Research Centre, the International Energy Agency, several European Transmission System Operators (Austrian Power Grid, Transnet BW etc.), Canadian Energy Regulator, and companies such as Shell and Saudi Aramco. In the field of energy security, JRC has used PyPSA-Eur for the resilience assessment of a power system due to disruption of interconnecting power lines [2].

The model employed was PyPSA-Eur that provides an optimization model of the European electricity transmission system (above 200 kV) with high spatial and temporal resolution, employing linear optimal power flow (LOPF), integrating detailed data on generation, transmission, demand, and flexibility options. It is built upon existing power plant fleets and transmission grid topology and considers the hourly availability profiles of renewable energy sources (based on historical weather data) and detailed electricity demand time series. The PyPSA-Eur model workflow has been validated by contrasting the outcomes of power network optimization against the historical behaviour of the European power system (2019) [3].

Beyond the electricity grid, PyPSA-Eur sector coupling expands the model into a fully integrated, multi-sector energy system. This configuration couples the electricity sector with other demand-side sectors, particularly with the gas sector. By co-optimizing these sectors, the model captures crucial cross-sectoral synergies.

In this paper, we leverage these two configurations to simulate targeted system disruptions, from asset failures and transmission bottlenecks to sudden supply shocks.

- The electricity-only model isolates the immediate vulnerabilities of the power grid. The model was customised to enlarge spatial resolution in the Nordic region (111 nodes in Norway, Sweden and Finland), and temporal resolution (1hour, during a 3-month period).
- The *sector-coupled* (gas – electricity) model allows us to observe how shocks propagate across the wider energy economy and capture multi-vector energy interdependencies. This model worked with 1 node per zone, 24-hour resolution.

The model was updated according to demand and capacity patterns for 2026 (based on European Resource Adequacy Assessment 2024) [4]. Three outcomes were assessed: energy generation (energy flow, energy mix), electricity non served and electricity price.

The modelling framework was applied to three exercise injects which had particular analytical significance.

- Northern Norway blackout - A sub-station failure in northern Norway triggered a regional outage. At the same time, two Swedish nuclear power plants were put on standby to allow immediate inspection of nuclear vessels after a crack was found in one unit. The modelling aimed to analyse islanding operation and the cross-border propagation effects of these simultaneous events.
- Severe gas disruption – An assessment of a complete halt to Norwegian gas exports to Europe following an explosion in an under-sea pipeline. The scenario was examined with the PyPSA-Eur power-flow model (capturing reductions in gas-fired electricity generation) and a sector-coupled gas–electricity model. In the electricity-only model, generation cuts were assumed for gas plants in Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Poland and the Netherlands; the coupled model enabled evaluation of multi-vector cascading impacts.
- Intense solar storm – A geomagnetic event that reduced Norway’s generation capacity by 95 % and lowered output in Finland and Sweden by 30 %. The injection tested the mechanisms in place for high-impact, low-probability scenarios, with consequences extending beyond electricity

The modelling outputs proved instrumental not readily discernible through qualitative scenario analysis alone — in particular, the mechanisms by which disturbances propagate across national boundaries and across energy sectors, manifested through electricity price spikes and supply adequacy shortfalls. These outputs directly informed scenario design and enabled the systematic identification of critical network elements and potential cascading failure pathways.

The findings from CORE 25-A demonstrate that European maritime and energy systems can no longer rely on isolated, efficiency-driven safeguards. The exercise highlighted the need for a comprehensive, resilience-oriented posture integrating civilian, military, and private-sector actors across

the full emergency management cycle. Six priority areas emerged: (i) enhanced intelligence sharing and AI-driven anomaly detection through integrated maritime surveillance platforms; (ii) layered resilience measures encompassing protection, response, and restoration phases, including interoperable technologies and regional spare-part pools; (iii) preparedness for emerging threats including advanced drone systems, and sophisticated cyber-attacks; (iv) upgraded multi-domain maritime situational awareness through expanded AIS coverage, GNSS hardening, and multi-sensor data fusion; (v) robust strategic communication frameworks with pre-approved multilingual messaging and redundant public alert channels; and (vi) regulatory guidelines to address evolving threats such as unmanned systems, contested maritime zones, or the protection of critical infrastructure in exclusive economic zones and international waters. The Exercise Report provides broader information about the key takeaways and conclusions [5]

The integration of structured tabletop exercises with targeted quantitative energy system modelling represents a methodological contribution to resilience analysis, enabling systematic, evidence-based identification of vulnerabilities that qualitative approaches alone cannot fully capture. Similar works with excellent results have been already showcased in previous tabletop exercises [6][6][8] This combined approach offers a replicable framework for assessing hybrid threats to critical maritime energy infrastructure across complex, multi-actor security environments.

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Towards a simulation and optimisation framework for the role of vessels in crisis management

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Abstract—Despite the increasing number of publications and research projects in disaster and crisis management and the importance of maritime logistics for many countries around the world, vessels and ships are hardly considered in (humanitarian) operations research (OR). In this ongoing research, we develop a framework for the role of vessels in crisis management and propose suitable OR models and approaches to solve the corresponding decision and planning problems.

Index Terms—simulation, optimisation, crisis and disaster management, framework, vessels

I. INTRODUCTION

The importance of crisis and disaster management has increased in recent months and years, and with it the number of research projects and publications in that area. Operations research (OR) methodologies, such as mathematical modelling and simulation, offer valuable tools to support all stages of the crisis management lifecycle [1]. Humanitarian logistics and disaster management are well-established application areas within OR. Publications address many different decision and planning problems ranging from volunteer management, resource location planning, patient transport, to infrastructure planning, food logistics, or patient care [2], [3]. Despite the vast variety of research topics and the similarly strong research focus within OR on maritime logistics, vessels and ships are hardly considered in humanitarian OR. One of the very few potential topics that has been studied is providing decision support for maritime search and rescue operations. Razi and Karatas propose a multi-objective model for locating search and rescue boats, for example, and choose as objectives the minimisation of response time to incidents, fleet operating cost, and mismatch between the workload of boats and the operation capacity hours [4]. Wu et al. also present a multi-objective resource allocation decision model for search and rescue missions as part of maritime emergencies [5]. The authors use reinforcement learning as a basis for their research and apply their approach to two real-world case studies that occurred in Chinese and Taiwanese waters. As one of very few publications on maritime emergency resource allocation, Zhang et al. addresses the aspect of uncertainty and proposes a robust optimisation approach which the authors apply to a case study from China [6]. Bersani et al. consider the emergency resource allocation problem for ports storing hazardous mate-

rials [7]. In their proposed model, they take first responders, fire fighters, and the dynamic nature of hazardous material accidents into account, applying their research to a port in Northern Italy. Mass evacuations from a remote location by helicopter or ship are addressed by Rempel and Shiell [8]. The authors propose an Approximate Dynamic Programming approach to solve the formulated Markov Decision Process and compare the resulting policy to several benchmark policies using a set of instances with different numbers of helicopters and ships.

II. FRAMEWORK OUTLINE

For developing the framework outline, we loosely follow the work of vom Brocke et al. [9]. We first started with an explorative literature review on the topic collecting first publications to develop a first draft of the framework and to guide the following structured literature review in EBSCO with the search string "(maritime OR port OR vessel OR ship) AND (resilience OR security) AND (emergency OR crisis OR disaster) AND (patient OR care OR health) AND (manag* OR optimis* OR simulat* OR decision OR planning OR model*)". The search led also to the discovery of an interesting publication on cruise disaster relief supply chain planning [10].

A subsequent structured literature review was performed using the WebOfScience data base and the following search string: TS = ((maritime OR port OR vessel OR ship) AND (resilien* OR security OR emergency OR cris* OR disaster) AND (patient* OR care OR health) AND (manag* OR optimis* OR simulat* OR decision OR planning OR model*)). As the search found 3328 publications, a detailed description and summary of the search is omitted in this work and left for future research.

Building on the results of the explorative and structured literature reviews, we propose the following ground structure for a framework to model the role of vessels in crisis management, involving the following five different dimensions:

- First dimension - occurrence: emergency in a vessel vs. a vessel affected by a disaster vs. a vessel supporting disaster management.

- Second dimension - task: search and rescue vs. providing personnel or resources/materials to a disaster site vs. transport of patients vs. other
- Third dimension - focus: use of vessels vs. water network infrastructure.
- Fourth dimension - planning problem: location planning vs. routing vs. scheduling vs. other.
- Fifth dimension - methodology: simulation vs. optimisation vs. other.

On the first dimension, we differentiate between 1) a crisis on a vessel, e.g. a pandemic outbreak or a fire, 2) a (natural or man-made) disaster in a port or on the water (e.g. flooding), or 3) a disaster that does not affect a vessel, but for which a vessel can be used to provide support. The second dimension looks at the main service types a vessel can offer, which are 1) search and rescue of missing persons, 2) transporting personnel, e.g. volunteers and / or resources, e.g. food or medical equipment, to a disaster site, 3) transporting patients, e.g. from a disaster site to a safe region, and 4) all other potential tasks a vessel could fulfil during a crisis. The third dimension takes a broader perspective again regarding the logistics, as 1) a vessel is used to provide a service, or 2) the water infrastructure used by vessels is analysed, e.g. regarding the availability of ports, the matching of the water level to ship heights, or the passability of bridges. The targeted planning problem forms the fourth dimension. Typical planning problems are 1) location planning, 2) routing, 3) scheduling or 4) other, e.g. assignment planning. The fifth dimension finally concerns the methodology used to address the problem, i.e. 1) simulation, 2) optimisation or 3) other, e.g. a hybrid approach.

Publications on simulation and optimisation problems targeting the use of vessels for crisis management can now be categorised using the framework and linked to one element of each dimension. Of course, the framework can also be used to describe problems that have not been addressed in the literature yet.

Objectives for corresponding mathematical models or heuristics to solve planning problems that address different combinations of entries on the three levels include:

- maximising patient survival or patient outcomes,
- minimising resources or costs,
- minimising response times,
- maximising utilisation.

III. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

With the exception of decision support for maritime search and rescue missions and a few publications on maritime emergency logistics, vessels are currently overlooked within the (humanitarian) OR community. Therefore, we started developing a framework for the role of vessels in crisis management with the aim of providing a set of optimisation and simulation models along the crisis management cycle.

The first iteration of the framework development relied solely on the results of several literature reviews. In a next step, we plan to conduct (online) interviews and focus group

discussions with experts and practitioners working in humanitarian and maritime logistics, first from Germany and then internationally, to extend and adapt the framework with a focus on impact and practical relevance. As an important part of the framework, modelling guidelines will be derived, and mathematical models and simulations will be developed and implemented for exemplary decision and planning problems, tested in case studies with data from German and international settings. In addition, we aim to analyse the literature found in the WebOfScience search in future detail and use it to derive gaps and opportunities for new models and approaches to support the use of vessels in crisis management.

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Data Analytics & Intelligent Systems

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The role of muon-based applications to imaging and PNT in the maritime sector

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The presentation focusses on two applications of muon-based technologies, namely muon attenuation tomography (also known as “muography”) and muon-based positioning, navigation and timing (PNT). Results from previous programmes of work are presented, and future potential applications of these methods to the maritime sector are discussed.

Keywords—muons, muography, muon tomography, PNT

I. EXTENDED ABSTRACT - INTRODUCTION

Muons are elementary particles that are created in the Earth’s atmosphere. With properties similar to those of a heavy electron, muons are particles which are both highly penetrating and plentiful, the flux at sea level typically being 1 per square centimetre per minute. Collectively, these properties can be exploited in two different ways, namely:

- **Muon attenuation tomography:** muons are highly penetrating and plentiful, and so, via a process similar in principle to an X-ray, muons are able to return information on density changes in an object of interest. It is worth noting two key differences between muon attenuation tomography and a medical X-ray: in the case of an X-ray the beam of penetrating particles has to come from a man-made source, in the case of muon attenuation tomography that source is free. However, unlike an X-ray, with muon attenuation tomography one is limited to looking up or towards the horizon to image, i.e. it is not possible to look down since muons cannot pass through the Earth.
- **Positioning, Timing and Navigation (PNT):** The same properties of muons, i.e. plentiful and highly-penetrating offers an appealing application within PNT, of particular interest is that muons cannot be spoofed or jammed - something that GPS/GNSS is susceptible to. Previous work carried out in this field had exploited so-called multi-lateration techniques between muon sensors in known locations and sensors in unknown locations with timing information being recorded with high-frequency clocks running appropriate protocols and being transmitted via standard techniques, such as radio or acoustic. This offers a unique system capable of transferring either static or relative positional information to a GPS/GNSS denied location.

II. MUON ATTENUATION TOMOGRAPHY

Geoptic is a UK company spin-out from 3 UK universities and has significant experience of practically

applying muon attenuation tomography to various challenges across multiple sectors. Some of these are discussed below.

A substantial programme of ongoing muon tomographic studies is taking place, primarily on the UK’s national railway network. In total, more than 20 in-service structures such as tunnels, bridges and viaducts have been imaged since 2019. Here results from muon attenuation tomography data-taking campaigns are primarily being used to educate the prioritisation process for maintenance and remedial works.

An example of the unseen density differences that muon tomography can observe in such structures is provided in Figure 1 whereby features, such as a full-height hidden shaft, which was merely suspected from old historical records, have been confirmed without invasive work on the structure having to take place.

Figure 1: 3D visualisation of density anomalies in a railway tunnel in the UK using muon tomography.

A further case study which exemplifies the diverse application space of muon-based imaging is that of a campaign undertaken in Norway during which time muon attenuation tomography was used to observe the density change in the subsurface as a consequence of CCS injection. In this instance muon tomography sensors were co-deployed with industry-standard 4D-seismic instrumentation with both techniques observing a few percent density change in the subsurface with excellent agreement [2]. Of particular note here is the fact that, whilst the 4D seismic technique is heavily used in the oil and gas industry, it is episodic in nature, whilst muon tomography is a continuous and thus complementary method.

A further potential application of muon attenuation tomography is that of applying it for studies of geological structures and features. In this respect, there are ongoing discussions around the potential to use muon attenuation tomography to help address safeguarding within the nuclear waste industry. Figure 2 demonstrates an example of the unique information that muon tomography can provide,

whereby the presence of unknown karstic voiding (assumed to be spherical in shape for this study) in a candidate disposal site is identified. In this case it is assumed that detectors are located several hundred metres underground, hence the long measurement times.

Figure 2: Identification of spherically-shaped karstic voiding in a geological overburden.

Over the past decade the number of applications of muon tomography has increased significantly. A useful summary of this case be found in this IAEA report [3].

In the context of the maritime sector there is a long list of potential applications of muon attenuation tomography, which are only just starting to be considered, these include, for example:

- harbour wall and coastal defence imaging: the effect of constant wave motion on sea walls and other natural coastal barriers is well-established. The ability of muon tomography to detect density changes in objects could mean that unseen coastal defence erosion could be detected, and remedial action taken, before serious degradation takes place;
- wind turbine base assessment: constant aerodynamic forces and cyclic load fatigue can lead to accelerated wear and tear on the wind turbine piling, risking - in extreme cases - catastrophic failure. It is possible that muon tomography could become part of the raft of diagnostic tools currently used to identify such problems;
- enhanced understanding of the seabed subsurface: in highly turbid environment where visibility is poor imaging techniques sensitive to density changes, such as muon tomography, could be used, e.g. for looking for boulders prior to wind turbine emplacement;
- a security sensor system for littoral or harbour ingress detection: an array of muon sensors placed at a strategically-sensitive ingress point could have sensitivity to passing, submerged and otherwise non-detectable craft due to their density.

III. POSITIONING, TIMING AND NAVIGATION (PNT)

As mentioned above, in addition to their use in measuring density changes in objects, muons can also be applied to Position, Navigation and Timing (PNT).. Collectively, the properties of muons being both plentiful and highly-penetrating can, in principle, be exploited to provide PNT in environments where GPS/GNSS is either denied (“jamming”) or otherwise impaired (“spoofing”).

Geoptic has previously successfully implemented a technique known as multi-lateration whereby muon sensors in known locations are used to identify the location of a sensor in unknown position(s) with timing information being recorded with high-frequency clocks running, e.g. suitable protocols such as WhiteRabbit and being transmitted via standard techniques, such as radio or acoustic.

Field trials have been carried out involving muon-sensitive instrumentation being deployed in a number of environments where positioning information can be challenging, these include underwater deployments where reference detectors were deployed on a frozen lake in Northern Finland, and a roving (unknown position) sensor was deployed in the water under the frozen ice surface of the same lake (see figure 3 for individual trilateral vs. theoretical x, y and z co-ordinate reconstruction).

Figure 3: Underwater deployment of “roving” muon sensor for PNT tests.

Results from the underwater deployment field trial - which was the most challenging and realistic deployment since the clocks were desynchronised and all muon combinations considered - indicate that ground truth information was reconstructed with an average positional error of 2.4 m (which would have been 1 m except for one outlier)

Alternative techniques that do not require high-precision clocks are now under consideration.

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WaveGuard: Real-Time On-Board Detection of Missing Persons in Side-Scan Sonar Imagery

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Abstract—Locating missing persons in underwater environments is a time-critical task for which side-scan sonar (SSS) is the primary sensing modality. However, interpreting SSS imagery is cognitively demanding and error-prone, especially under operational pressure. Most existing work focuses on offline analysis or model performance with little consideration for direct deployment in real-world search-and-rescue (SAR) operations. In this work, we present WaveGuard, an AI-based system designed for the automated detection of missing persons in SAR imagery. It is intended for direct use in SAR missions and can operate on board search vessels. In order to train a deep learning-based object detection model, we first collected a dataset that represented operational conditions. The system is optimized for inference on embedded edge devices, enabling deployment in remote environments without reliance on cloud infrastructure. A key feature of the proposed approach is that it does not require integration with proprietary sonar software. Sonar imagery is extracted automatically from display outputs in a manufacturer-independent manner, enabling plug-and-play operation across different sonar devices. Additionally, the dataset supports structured training scenarios for SAR personnel, enabling the systematic assessment and improvement of human detection performance. This work presents a practical, deployable AI system that bridges the gap between sonar-based detection research and real-world SAR applications.

Index Terms—Machine Learning, Search and Rescue, Side-Scan-Sonar

I. INTRODUCTION

Underwater search and rescue (SAR) operations present a uniquely challenging perceptual environment. Side scan sonar (SSS) enables large-area aquatic searches with well performing imaging of the riverbed or seabed [1]. In contrast, the interpretation of SSS imagery is a demanding task requiring sustained expert attention under high-stress field conditions. Human fatigue, variability in operator experience, and the sheer volume of imagery generated during active searches contribute to missed detections [2]. Despite advances in computer vision and deep learning for aerial and terrestrial SAR, the

application of automated object detection to underwater sonar imagery has received comparatively little systematic attention [3]. This work addresses that gap through a holistic, end-to-end detection system encompassing dataset construction, algorithm development, simulation-augmented training, edge deployment, automated image acquisition, and operator training.

II. METHODS

A. Data Collection

A dedicated dataset of side scan sonar imagery was collected specifically for the purpose of missing person detection. Data acquisition campaigns were conducted under controlled and operationally representative conditions. These campaigns involved capturing SSS sweeps in various bodies of water, with human-like dolls acting as surrogates for submerged persons. Annotations were produced by domain experts, labelling bounding regions around target echoes and associated acoustic shadows. The dataset spans a range of sonar frequencies, depths, sediment types, and target orientations, ensuring coverage of the variability encountered in real SAR deployments. Attention was paid to the challenge of class imbalance, as positive instances of person-like targets are rare relative to background seafloor clutter, boulders, and debris. This dataset is larger than comparable ones from Finland [4] and England [5], respectively, and can therefore be used to train a data-driven algorithm to locate missing persons. Our dataset is already publicly available to support reproducible research in this area [6].

B. Object Detection on Sonar Images

A neural network based object detection pipeline was trained and evaluated on the collected dataset. To compensate for the limited amount of real-world data, a physics-informed sonar simulation pipeline was used to create more training samples. Realistic background scenes were created by compositing simulated human targets with a range of

body poses, orientations, and burial states. Combining real and synthetic training data improved detection performance by approximately 2.3% in mAP50 and 4% in recall, enhancing the model’s ability to detect human targets in sonar imagery. This finding is consistent with our previous work, which highlighted the importance of simulation realism [7].

C. Edge Deployment

A core design requirement of the system is the ability to perform inference in real time aboard the survey vessel, without dependence on cloud connectivity. The trained detection model was optimised for edge deployment, and exported to a runtime-efficient format suitable for embedded GPU hardware. The deployed system processes incoming SSS data in a streaming fashion, generating bounding box predictions and confidence scores overlaid on the live sonar images. An alert mechanism flags high-confidence detections for immediate operator review, reducing the cognitive burden of continuous screen monitoring during extended search operations.

D. Automatic Viewport Detection

A practical challenge in deploying image analysis software alongside commercial sonar equipment is the variety of proprietary display formats and software interfaces used by different manufacturers, as well as the various user preferences. Rather than requiring manual configuration or custom integration for each sonar system, this work introduces an automatic viewport detection module that analyses the screen output of the sonar device. Once the sonar viewport has been identified, the raw pixel content of the SSS image is extracted and passed to the detection pipeline. This process does not modify the manufacturer’s software stack, enabling non-invasive integration with different commercially available sonar units. This plug-and-play architecture greatly reduces the barriers to adoption for operational SAR teams.

III. KEY RESULTS

This dataset has facilitated significant advancements in the development of an object recognition algorithm that is designed to provide active support to emergency responders in the field, as well as to enhance their training.

A. Missing Person Detection

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE METRICS OF OBJECT DETECTION MODELS TRAINED AND EVALUATED ON REAL SONAR IMAGES FROM THE AQUASCAN-1K DATASET. [6]

Model	Precision	Recall	mAP50	mAP50:95
YOLOv11	0.734	0.741	0.774	0.401
RT-DETR	0.782	0.861	0.867	0.482
RF-DETR	0.849	0.889	0.883	0.518

Table I presents the performance of CNN-based (YOLO), hybrid (RT-DETR), and Transformer-based (RF-DETR) object detection models on the AquaScan-1K dataset [6]. The results indicate that Transformer-based and hybrid approaches achieve

superior detection performance, benefiting from their global attention mechanisms. In particular, the RF-DETR model demonstrates improved performance by achieving fewer false positives and lower miss rates in human target detection.

B. Search and Rescue Training

Recognising that automated detection systems are most effective when used alongside with well-trained human operators, the collected dataset was also used to develop a gamified training programme for SAR personnel. The training protocol exposes participants to a curated library of annotated SSS images. Selecting a specific part of the dataset allows it to be incorporated into a training session or provides an opportunity for a quick refresher in between sessions. It is expected that the combination of automated algorithmic detection and better-trained human reviewers will yield a substantially higher overall system sensitivity than either component alone. This establishes a compelling case for the joint deployment of AI-assisted tools and structured human training in operational SAR settings.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we demonstrate how SAR teams can be supported most effectively during search operations. Thanks to its integration with existing systems and its ability to overlay detection data without requiring complete replacement, we anticipate that emergency responders will welcome the system. Future work will involve expanding the dataset to include additional environmental conditions, as well as conducting a prospective evaluation of the complete system in live search operations in collaboration with SAR organisations.

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Underwater material identification using cosmic-ray induced gamma spectroscopy

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Abstract—Detecting and classifying materials and objects underwater remains a significant challenge for conventional acoustic and geophysical techniques, particularly in complex environments and at greater depths. This research aims to investigate the potential of cosmic-ray induced gamma spectroscopy (CRIGS) as a complementary, non-destructive method for material identification. This method relies on detecting secondary photons produced by muon interactions with matter such as bremsstrahlung, annihilation, and muon capture which allow materials to be distinguished either by energy-specific gamma-ray emissions or by the photon production rate. Simulation studies are performed using Geant4, considering various materials (lead, copper, aluminium, and iron) and different water depths. This method, if combined with existing conventional acoustic or geophysical techniques, can provide additional, in-depth knowledge about material detection underwater.

Index Terms—cosmic-ray induced gamma spectroscopy, non-destructive testing, material identification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Detecting objects and materials underwater is a difficult task and, to this day, has generally been performed using widely established acoustic techniques such as sonar systems or sub-bottom profilers, as well as other geophysical methods including magnetometers or electromagnetic induction. While these techniques remain valuable for material detection, they are limited by sediment type, signal attenuation, and environmental interference [1], [2]. Acoustic methods in particular are affected among others by frequency-dependent attenuation and scattering in water and sediments, which can complicate signal interpretation in complex environments. As a result, data analysis becomes challenging for complex, multi-element structures or objects located at large depths. Cosmic-ray induced gamma spectroscopy (CRIGS), a technique that exploits gamma-rays generated by cosmic-ray interactions with matter, is conceptually related to other cosmic-ray imaging methods such as muography [3]–[5] but relies on secondary particle generation using a range of interaction mechanisms. It is, however, subject to significant attenuation in water due to strong scattering and absorption of gamma radiation, which limits its effective range in underwater environments. Despite these constraints, CRIGS can provide complementary insight into material composition, particularly in contexts where cosmic-ray induced gamma emissions are detectable and can be reliably measured. Another benefit of using CRIGS is that, compared to other established underwater techniques that rely on artificial radiation sources such as X-rays or UV

light in optical methods or active acoustic emission including sonar systems, it does not require the deployment of an artificial radiation source and therefore minimizes additional environmental impact and safety concerns associated with active emitters. This method, when used in combination with sonar or geophysical systems, can provide highly valuable information about material types underwater.

II. COSMIC-RAY INDUCED GAMMA SPECTROSCOPY

The main focus of this research is to present the concept of underwater material characterisation using cosmic-ray-induced gamma spectroscopy. This novel and innovative technology has the potential to revolutionise the way we identify and characterise materials underwater.

CRIGS uses gamma-rays which are emitted when muons from cosmic air showers, interact with matter. The cosmic air shower is a secondary cascade of particles towards the surface being a result of interactions between stable, charged particles from astrophysical sources (mainly protons) high up in Earth's atmosphere with atoms and molecules. At the sea level, the most abundant detectable air shower particle is the muon with a flux of around 1 per cm² per minute. In addition to their natural occurrence, muons from air showers also hold a high penetration power. These combined features make muons an ideal natural passive radiation source for detecting objects and materials in the ocean and on the seabed.

Due to the interactions of muons with the surrounding matter, additional secondary particles, including mostly photons, neutrons or electrons, are generated through processes such as bremsstrahlung, annihilation, and muon capture. This research focuses exclusively on secondary photons, whose energies and kinematics depend strongly on the target material. Bremsstrahlung and annihilation are the primary interactions generating these photons, with additional contributions from muon capture and radioactive decay.

A key advantage of muon capture is that it produces gamma-rays with distinct energies of the target material, allowing for clear distinction from the ambient background. Muon bremsstrahlung, on the other hand, does not yield gamma-rays with well-defined energies, instead, it occurs with a probability that is strongly dependent on the intrinsic material properties, mainly its density and atomic number. As a result, spectroscopic and kinematic analysis of secondary photons provides highly specific information about the material composition of the examined object. Previous research has shown

the feasibility of this concept through various extensive simulation studies, as well as experimental measurements under laboratory conditions [6]–[13]. This work is the worlds-first study to prove the applicability of this technique in underwater conditions.

III. SIMULATION STUDIES

Simulation studies are carried out using the Monte Carlo simulation toolkit Geant4 [14], which is designed for modeling the passage of particles through matter. Initial simulations are performed in air, where simple geometric objects made out of different materials, such as lead, copper, iron and aluminum, are used as the targets. Subsequently, the simulations are extended to underwater conditions, where simulations are conducted within a water basin at various depths of 0.5 m, 2.5 m and 4.5 m. The energy and kinematic properties of secondary gamma-rays emitted from the target are recorded using detectors positioned at various distances. Using a preliminary spectroscopy method, the selected materials are successfully distinguished from one another showing the feasibility of CRIGS in the underwater domain. These preliminary results open a new path to scaling up dataset generation as well as applying machine learning techniques adapted from muon-scattering tomography and anomaly detection, to achieve more robust material differentiation [15]–[17]. This approach will enable effective scaling to multi-element objects and greater depths, while supporting real-time underwater anomaly flagging

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, cosmic-ray induced gamma spectroscopy offers a promising complementary approach for underwater material detection. By using naturally occurring radiation, it enables passive non-destructive analysis while providing material-specific information that is difficult to obtain with conventional techniques. When combined with established acoustic and geophysical methods, it has the potential to significantly improve detection capabilities in challenging underwater environment. Future studies and experimental tests under controlled conditions are planned in order to further assess its practical applicability and usability. Additionally, implementing machine learning techniques in further analysis would result in more robust material differentiation.

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Towards Short-Term Forecasts of Sea Ice Conditions for Ship Navigation in the Baltic Sea

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Abstract— Navigating in the seasonally ice-covered waters of the Baltic Sea is challenging and risky due to the constantly changing nature of sea ice. Winds can push floes together or pull them apart, forming dense pack ice in some areas and natural openings in others. To improve safety and efficiency, we present a new conceptual approach for generating high-resolution, predictive ice maps for the Baltic Sea. Using artificial intelligence, we derive critical ice properties from spaceborne Synthetic Aperture Radar data – in particular the stage of development. These properties are integrated into a newly developed sea ice drift forecast model to generate hourly forecasts of ice conditions. The resulting dataset provides a detailed, forward-looking view of ice, helping optimize ship routes through ice-covered waters.

Keywords— Synthetic Aperture Radar, Maritime Situational Awareness, Ship Routing, Baltic Sea, Sea Ice Drift Forecast, Sea Ice Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

The navigation of ships in the seasonally ice-covered waters of the Baltic Sea places high demands on both humans and technology and is associated with significant risks. In this semi-enclosed sea, extreme wind events and wind-driven currents act on the ice cover, leading to rapid, dynamic changes in ice conditions. Within a few hours, converging forces can consolidate large masses of ice, forming pressure ridges where ice floes tilt upward or stack above and below one another. The resulting deformed ice can, in some cases, become impassable even for icebreakers [1]. Conversely, diverging forces in other areas can break apart continuous ice covers, creating leads and natural passages. For the safe and efficient navigation of ships in the Baltic, timely information regarding local ice drift and ice properties is therefore of critical importance.

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) satellites, such as TerraSAR-X or Sentinel-1 provide a reliable basis for large-scale sea ice monitoring in the Baltic Sea. Due to their ability to provide image data of the oceans and frozen waters regardless of cloud cover or solar illumination, SAR observations have been an integral component for national ice

services for decades. These data allow ice services to produce expert-level charts that distinguish between ice types, providing a vital safety framework for vessels navigating in ice-infested Baltic waters.

However, SAR images provide only a snapshot of the surroundings. By their very nature, they are static. Furthermore, data delivery is subject to latency; the process of downlinking, processing, and delivering data to the user often takes around three hours or longer (depending on the mission). During this interval, the highly dynamic ice conditions may have already shifted, meaning the derived insights may be outdated by the time they are applied.

In this study, we present a novel method for projecting SAR-based sea ice information, specifically classification by stage of development, into the future, involving sea ice drift forecast data. This approach allows the generation of spatio-temporal datasets with hourly resolution that show upcoming sea ice conditions, thereby forming the basis for automatic ship route calculation.

Chapter II briefly outlines the sea ice classification, and Chapter III the method for generating the spatio-temporal datasets.

II. SAR-BASED SEA ICE CLASSIFICATION FOR THE BALTIC

Sea ice is traditionally classified according to its stage of development. This classification usually follows the international standard of the WMO (World Meteorological Organization), which ensures globally consistent ice charts. Consequently, there are numerous scientific publications describing various approaches to determine the stage of development from SAR data, which are comprehensively summarized in [2].

In [3], we demonstrated the effectiveness of UNET++ for sea ice mapping in terms of its stage of development. In this contribution, we present a significantly enhanced methodology specifically tailored to map sea ice in the Baltic Sea. Basically, the new method generates sea ice polygons to outline areas of similar ice conditions and employs artificial

intelligence to classify these areas. The methodology has recently been integrated into the operational processing chain at the DLR ground segment in Neustrelitz, providing automated sea ice maps in near real-time directly to the German ice service of the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, BSH).

III. FORECASTING THE SEA ICE CONDITIONS

As mentioned before, the expected future sea ice conditions are of great interest to maritime navigation and are essential for automatic route planning. Therefore, a newly presented method utilizes specially developed sea ice drift forecasts for the Baltic Sea to project the derived SAR-based sea ice maps hourly into the near future. In detail, we use polygonised sea ice information to extract corner points, which are then advected using a Lagrangian tracking approach based on the drift forecast.

The resulting spatio-temporal dataset, termed the 'Dynamic Ice Map', overall maintains the high spatial resolution of the original SAR-derived sea ice maps. It compensates for the delay between data acquisition and delivery to the user, and also allows for a detailed look into the future.

IV. OUTLOOK

By bridging the gap between static SAR-based observations and the dynamic requirements of modern navigation, the presented approach has the potential to improve situational awareness. The integration of high-resolution SAR data with predictive modeling not only improves operational safety but also provides a robust foundation for future autonomous maritime systems in the Baltic Sea.

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Maritime Security Technology

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Space-Derived Telemanipulation for Underwater UXO Recovery: Testbed Development for Maritime Security Applications

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Abstract—Teleoperation with haptic force feedback has emerged as a proven technique for executing tasks remotely, particularly in environments that are hazardous or inaccessible to humans. Recent Space-to-Ground demonstrations like the *Surface Avatar* mission have shown that even with high communication-delay links, stable teleoperation can be achieved, supporting shared-autonomy algorithms that provide partial intelligence and automation. These advances can benefit also other applications like the recovery of underwater unexploded ordnances (UXO), a domain that still relies heavily on manual diver intervention due to the required high fidelity. To adapt space-derived teleoperation methods for tasks underwater, this work presents a compact hardware testbed for development and experimentation. The setup consists of an underwater robotic arm equipped with a gripper, coupled to a haptic interface reflecting forces to the operator, all housed within an aquarium. Within this environment, controllers can be implemented and tested including functionalities like buoyancy compensation, realistic haptic feedback to tackle the unique challenges of submerged manipulation. This testbed lays the groundwork for rigorous evaluation and eventual operational deployment in maritime security contexts.

I. INTRODUCTION

The presence of over 1.6 million tons of unexploded ordnance (UXO) in European waters poses significant threats to maritime security, offshore infrastructure, and marine ecosystems [1]. Safely recovering these corroding munitions is challenging: it demands precise force control and acute situational awareness to avoid triggering unstable ordnance. While trained divers' dexterity and force sensitivity remain unmatched by technology, modern recovery strategies increasingly deploy autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) and remotely operated vehicles (ROVs). These robotic platforms excel at detecting and manipulating larger, less delicate objects, yet they typically lack sophisticated manipulation capabilities and haptic force-feedback, limiting their effectiveness in high-risk UXO operations [2].

To enhance underwater manipulation, we leverage techniques pioneered for space missions, where the environments can be intricate, and interaction forces must be conveyed from the remote site to the operator despite high time delays

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Fig. 1. Miniature testbed environment developed to enable testing telemanipulation methods for underwater UXO recovery.

and package losses. The recent *Surface Avatar* demonstration mission showed that astronauts aboard the ISS can stably teleoperate a team of Earth-based robots at the German Aerospace Center (DLR) for complex tasks that require force feedback [3]. Advanced teleoperation methods combining impedance control and haptic force rendering, enabled robot collaboration, precise insertion and inspection tasks [4], [5]. These same methods hold promise for UXO clearance, but they must be systematically adapted to the underwater environment, where fluid dynamics, buoyancy, and poor visibility impose additional constraints on force sensing [6], control stability, and operator awareness.

To address these challenges, we developed a testbed as part of DLR's *WATERSIDE* project [7] for adapting space-derived teleoperation controllers to underwater UXO recovery. The testbed integrates a robotic arm with a gripper connected to a haptic force feedback device to render interaction forces to the operator. The robot can be submerged in an aquarium environment. Using this test setup shall result in multiple contributions: (1) the first systematic adaptation of space robotics teleoperation methods for underwater UXO recovery, (2) adaptation of advanced impedance controllers for underwater manipulation of unstable ordnances, (3) development of UXO-specific force guided trajectories known virtual fixtures (VF) [8], and (4) establishment of a testbed platform for continuous development and evaluation.

II. TESTBED DESIGN

The testbed implements space-derived telemanipulation techniques in a controlled environment that simulates key aspects of underwater UXO recovery operations. The testbed is setup to mount a multi-DOF robotic arm with a gripper as end effector. It is mounted in a 100 cm × 70 cm × 70 cm

aquarium filled with either fresh or saline water. A safety cage surrounds the tank, serving both as containment and as a robust mounting platform for the arm, additional sensors, and cameras (see Fig. 1). A haptic input device can be connected to serve as input device for the operator and reflect forces to support the underwater manipulation. Different haptic devices can be used in the setup, reflecting forces in at least three or six degrees of freedom and providing an input for the operator to close and open the gripper, e.g., Force Dimension’s lambda.7 [9]. Miniaturized UXO mock-ups, fabricated to match the shape, surface texture, and bulk density of real ordnance, can be placed within the tank to test the required manipulation tasks for underwater clearance. For initial controller validation and visualization, a simulation of the testbed with the robotic arm is implemented using MuJoCo [10] to serve as a digital twin, enabling safe testing before deployment on the physical hardware.

III. SENSOR IMPLEMENTATION

The testbed will also serve to identify the sensor suite required for effective teleoperation with high-fidelity haptic feedback underwater. In realistic maritime scenarios, a navigation network built around underwater vehicles will inevitably introduce non-negligible communication delays, making the controllers developed for space missions that are even stable under high unknown time-varying delays even more critical. By testing different latencies in the testbed’s communication loop, controller performance can be evaluated under various conditions and bandwidths. Other challenges that arise in underwater domains are low visibility caused by stirred-up sediment and continuous wave-induced disturbances, which require different sensor considerations than needed in space. The testbed will be used to investigate the use of underwater cameras combined with depth-sensing modalities like LiDAR or sonar to ensure reliable spatial data in turbid water through sensor fusion. This is crucial to identify munition objects and create a 3D point cloud of its shape needed to generate force feedback. Through systematic variation of visibility levels and sensor combinations, it can be investigated which data streams yield accurate information to enable resilient and efficient teleoperation.

IV. CONTROL ARCHITECTURE

The teleoperation architecture to control the robotic arm in the testbed is based on previous work developed for space applications [5], [11]. For tasks that are prone to collisions, the Time-Domain Passivity Approach-High Delay (TDPA-HD) [4] controller ensures safe environmental interactions and transparent force reflection, regardless of latency. Additionally, especially in the case of UXO recovery, the robot must be compliant enough to be safely maneuvered by the active disturbances underwater with potentially unstable munitions around, while retaining sufficient stiffness for high-precision manipulation. This can be realized using DLR’s Elasto-Plastic Robot Compliance (EPRC) [5], which can detect active environments and enable adaptive plastic compliance for evasive maneuvers to provide additional safety.

Additionally, UXO-specific Virtual Fixtures (VF) are implemented to support the user to safely approach munitions, especially when visibility is low and force feedback from the remote side may be limited. In these scenarios with high uncertainty in measurements and trajectories, recent methods allow to employ different probabilistic VFs [12], [8]. Even in uncertain environments, such fixtures will provide the best available guidance to the operator in obstructed interactions.

V. OUTLOOK

The presented testbed provides the essential bridge for transferring robust, delay-compensated controllers from space to underwater applications. It offers a scalable, observable tank environment that captures the complex hydrodynamics omitted by pure simulation. The modular design permits testing of different robots along with different haptic devices, injection of realistic communication delays, and systematic evaluation of sensor suites for low-visibility conditions. By validating force-feedback and manipulation strategies in this controlled setting, the testbed will pave the way for rapid, safe integration of commercial robotic platforms into maritime security operations and the cleaning of underwater environments.

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Denshi: An Innovative Wave Energy Buoy for Powering Maritime Protection

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Abstract—Denshi is an innovative wave energy buoy developed by Weco, designed to provide persistent, zero-fuel power for offshore maritime surveillance and protection equipment. Weighing less than 40 kilograms with a 1.0 meter diameter, Denshi is rapidly deployable from rigid inflatable boats (RIBs), autonomous vessels, or via aerial drop. Engineered with proven marine-grade materials to withstand storm conditions, the system delivers 5.1 Watts of continuous power at wave heights as low as 0.30 meters—validated at MARIN and at sea. When deployed as a swarm, Denshi units form a Distributed Electronic Warfare (DEW) Mesh: a self-sustaining, low-cost sensor network capable of persistent maritime surveillance over large offshore areas, including subsea cable routes and wind farm perimeters.

Keywords—wave energy, maritime surveillance, critical infrastructure, Denshi, remote power, Weco, DEW-Mesh, offshore security

I. INTRODUCTION

Rapid innovation in (unmanned) disruptive technologies pose a severe threat to assets onshore as well as offshore, such as subsea cables and infrastructure and energy assets such as wind farms. Traditional monitoring systems are CAPEX-intensive and immobile systems that are both vulnerable and suffer from low-rate incrementalism. Distributed networks of floating buoys provide a low-cost solution that can monitor large areas continuously as it is powered by omni present waves. This paper proposes a more distributed alternative, quickly deployable and powered by the Denshi wave energy buoy. A lightweight and low-cost wave energy converter that acts as a platform for a variety of sensors.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE: THE DEW-MESH

The proposed Denshi-powered Distributed Electronic Warfare (DEW) Mesh utilizes a swarm of Denshi buoys to create a persistent sensor web network. Each buoy acts as a semi-autonomous cell. In offshore situations, these nodes form a ‘barrier’ configuration. First versions of the system provide 5.1 Watt continuous output at any sea state and supports 3.5 Watts for sensing, 1.0 Watt for edge AI processing, and 0.6 Watts for data transmission.

III. TECHNICAL SCHEMATIC AND COMPONENTS

Denshi provides 99.9 percent uptime and delivers 5.1 Watts of continuous power already at 0.30 meter significant wave height. Power production was validated at MARIN and at sea, the system weighs less than 40 kilograms with a 1.0 meter diameter. Each Denshi-EW node integrates an energy conversion unit for heave-to-torque conversion,

battery system, an on-board computer and communication capabilities. Additional sensors such as hydrophones or cameras can be added to increase the autonomous capabilities of the system.

IV. COST ANALYSIS

Table I compares the Denshi-powered DEW Mesh (50 units) against a traditional more centralized coastal EW station.

TABLE I. COST COMPARISON: DEW MESH VS. CENTRALIZED STATION

Category	Distributed Mesh (50 Units)	Centralized Station (1 Unit)
CAPEX	€1,000,000	€45,000,000+
Installation	€150,000	€5,000,000
Maintenance (Annual)	€50,000	€1,200,000
Lifespan	5–8 years	20+ years
Total 5-Year Cost	€1.4 Million	€56 Million

V. EFFECTIVENESS COMPARISON

The distributed mesh offers graceful degradation; coverage remains high even if individual nodes are lost. Unlike centralized stations limited by the Earth’s curvature, mesh nodes operate at the perimeter, detecting low-altitude emissions. Furthermore, passive operation minimizes the electromagnetic signature, protecting the nodes from targeting.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY FOR THE NORTH SEA AND BALTIC REGION

Denshi is particularly suited for deployment across the North Sea and Baltic Sea regions, where dense offshore wind farm infrastructure and critical subsea cable networks require persistent, distributed monitoring. Nodes can be deployed in a ‘Zonal Guard’ pattern near subsea cable landings, offshore wind farms, and key maritime chokepoints, providing a zero-fuel tripwire for unauthorised surface and sub-surface activity. Future applications of the Denshi-powered DEW Mesh in these regions include EO/IR surveillance via triggered response, NAVWAR (Navigation Warfare), ASW (Anti-Submarine Warfare), DRFM (Digital Radio Frequency Memory), protocol jamming and passive RESM (Radar Electronic Support Measures).

Baltic Sea VDES R-Mode Testbed

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I. Introduction

Maritime navigation greatly depends on Global Satellite Navigation Systems (GNSS) such as GPS or Galileo. Recently it has become apparent that GNSS can be affected by outages, jamming, and spoofing. Especially the Baltic Sea area has been affected by jamming and spoofing. The critical nature of this threat was formally identified in a March 2025 joint communiqué by the IMO, ITU, and ICAO, which mandated that member states implement stringent GNSS spectrum protections and expedite the engineering of resilient Position, Navigation, and Timing (PNT) architectures. In direct response to these operational vulnerabilities, the IMO Maritime Safety Committee (MSC), during its 110th session, issued a formal directive to the Sub-Committee on Navigation, Communications and Search and Rescue (NCSR). This mandate requires the derivation and finalization of a comprehensive performance standard for R-Mode receivers, to be deliberated during the forthcoming 13th session of the NCSR. Such a desirable alternative method of localization that includes monitoring the integrity of GNSS as well as continued navigation with acceptable accuracy when GNSS become unavailable is called R-Mode (Ranging-Mode). R-Mode relies on extending existing maritime communication systems by a ranging component.

Two variations of the R-Mode concept are currently being developed.

- MF R-Mode is based on the IALA beacon DGNSS system that operates in the Medium Frequency band.
- VDES R-Mode, which is based on the VHF Data Exchange System (VDES) that operates in the VHF band.

Both systems are planned to coexist and supplement each other, with MF R-Mode covering longer distances and VDES R-Mode covering coastal areas. MF R-Mode already has an operational testbed in the Baltic Sea. VDES R-Mode however has so far only been demonstrated in short term setups.

In order to provide a better foundation for evaluating and demonstrating VDES R-Mode, also in conjunction with MF R-Mode, a testbed is being set up in the Baltic Sea.

II. Testbed design

The testbed consists of three fixed base stations positioned on islands in the Baltic Sea. The three locations

Fig. 1. The locations of the VDES R-Mode base stations. All three base stations are placed on islands in the Baltic Sea.

are:

- Karlshagen in the north of Usedom.
- Thiessow in the south of Rügen.
- Greifswalder Oie, an uninhabited island.

Figure 1 shows the locations of the base stations on a map. The locations were chosen due to their favorable geometry and due to the existing infrastructure of the German Federal Waterways and Shipping Administration.

Each station consists of the following hardware:

- Two VHF antennas. One for transmitting and one for monitoring purposes.
- A Kongsberg VDES BS620 base station that transmits the VDES R-Mode signals.
- An Ettus B210 SDR. Two receive channels are used on the SDR. One channel is connected to an RF coupler to directly monitor the transmitted signals from the Kongsberg base station. The second channel is connected to the VHF monitoring antenna.
- A rubidium clock that provides a 10 MHz reference signal to the Kongsberg base station and the GNSS

Fig. 3. The data recorded during the first test. Blue crosses show Karlshagen; red crosses show the Greifswalder Oie; and green crosses show Thiessow. The black lines are the references obtained from GNSS.

Fig. 2. The track of the ship during the crossing from the island to Karlshagen.

receiver.

- A Septentrio PolaRx4 GNSS receiver, used for monitoring the clock and for providing the SDR with a

timing reference.

- A small form factor computer to control the SDR.
- An LTE router to provide remote access.

Aside from providing the testbed area with VDES R-Mode signals, the setup offers the following opportunities:

- The GNSS receiver can be used to monitor the accuracy of the rubidium clock.
- The SDR in the base stations can be used to receive each others signals. This makes it possible to evaluate long term channel effects in between the stations. It can also be used to perform integrity checks on the signals transmitted in the testbed.
- The SDR also records the adjacent AIS band. Since all base stations are time synchronized this allows for research regarding the verification of AIS reports using Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA).

First results have been obtained using a temporary setup on a ship operated by the German Waterway administration (WSV). It is planned to equip the same ship with a more permanent receiver installation which will be able to record data sets whenever it is within the testbed area.

III. First results

A first dataset was collected using a ship with a temporary antenna and a B210 Software defined radio.

Figure 2 shows the track of the ship during data recording. The recording took place during a crossing from the Greifswalder Oie to Karlshagen. During the measurement, ranges and relative velocities were obtained for all three base stations. Figure 3 shows the results for the Karlshagen base station.

IV. Summary

A testbed for VDES R-Mode has been planned and set up in the Baltic Sea near Rügen. The planned testbed consists of three base stations each equipped with a GNSS receiver and an atomic clock for time synchronization. All three base stations are already operational. First results have been obtained with a ship of the German waterway administration. The long term installation of a receiver on the ship is planned.

Time Synchronization and Recovery Using R-Mode

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Abstract—Time synchronization is a fundamental requirement for modern maritime navigation, supporting accurate positioning, operational coordination, and navigational safety. Although Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) provide the primary source for positioning and timing, their susceptibility to interference, including jamming and spoofing, particularly in regions such as the Baltic Sea, has motivated the development of complementary technologies such as R-Mode. This work presents methods for extracting timing information from Minimum Shift Keying (MSK) signals used within the R-Mode system. It evaluates the achievable synchronization accuracy and investigates approaches for stabilizing a local clock oscillator using remote atomic clock references in order to maintain a stable and continuously updated time source.

Index Terms—PNT, R-Mode, MSK signals, maritime navigation, timing synchronization, GNSS backup

I. INTRODUCTION

While GNSS provides high accuracy and global coverage [1], its signals are inherently weak at the Earth's surface and therefore vulnerable to interference, jamming, spoofing, or signal obstruction [2] [3] [4]. These vulnerabilities pose significant risks for safety-critical systems, particularly in maritime environments where reliable navigation and timing are essential. Consequently, the development of complementary terrestrial technologies capable of maintaining PNT services during GNSS disruptions has increased in importance.

One promising approach is Ranging Mode (R-Mode), a terrestrial navigation concept designed to provide positioning and timing capabilities by reusing existing maritime radio infrastructure. In the Baltic Sea region, R-Mode implementations are based on medium-frequency (MF) maritime radio beacon transmissions that incorporate two signal components [2].

The first component consists of Minimum Shift Keying (MSK) signals used for broadcasting differential GNSS corrections in accordance with Radio Technical Commission for Maritime Services (RTCM) standards. These MSK-modulated transmissions provide a continuous data stream that can be processed to extract timing information [5]. The second component comprises continuous wave (CW) signals transmitted alongside the MSK signal, which serve as stable spectral references that allow precise phase measurements for ranging applications (See Fig. 1.). By combining the phase information from the CW tones with the timing information derived from the MSK signal, R-Mode systems enable terrestrial positioning and time synchronization capabilities.

Fig. 1. R-Mode spectrum, with the MSK at a 300,000 Hz carrier and the two continuous waves (CW) at 299,775 Hz and 300,225 Hz respectively

This work focuses specifically on the extraction of precise timing information from the MSK-modulated RTCM transmissions of maritime radio beacons operating in the Baltic Sea. The objective is to investigate methods for recovering accurate time references from these signals and to evaluate their suitability for stabilizing local oscillators relative to remote atomic clock references. Through analytical modeling, simulation, and experimental measurements, the study evaluates the feasibility of using terrestrial R-Mode signals as reliable timing sources, contributing to the development of resilient maritime PNT systems capable of operating independently of GNSS.

II. ACQUISITION OF ABSOLUTE TIME

DGNSS beacons broadcast corrective messages, and a parameter of interest is called the z-count [6]. This parameter alone cannot be used to extract absolute time because it does not represent the actual transmission time. Rather, it corresponds to the message generation time. For the purposes of this paper, the z-count will be considered the transmission time despite the fact that it is not designed to be. In the future, the R-Mode message 55 will be used to enhance the current DGNSS system. This message will be sent every minute, and the contained time will reflect the current R-Mode system time at transmission. This allows the user to unambiguously retrieve the absolute timing at reception. At the time of writing this paper, the R-Mode message 55 is not available, so the implementation is designed to work with R-Mode message 55 at its release. However, the implementation is currently being tested using the z-count parameter broadcast by existing DGNSS stations, assuming it represents the absolute time, solely as a proof of concept.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Fig. 2. True UTC time (red) and time extracted from the Groß Mohrdorf station (blue)

Fig. 3. Zoomed-in view of the first 10 minutes of the experiment (Fig. 2)

We were able to approximate the time using real measured signals. A residual bias remains after removing the outliers. The calculated bias between the extracted time and the actual UTC time is 18.91 s and the standard deviation is 0.50 s. The bias, visible as an offset between the true time (red line) and the extracted time (blue line), can be explained by many factors. A substantial part of it comes from the difference between UTC and GPS time of 18 seconds. Correcting for the constant GPS–UTC offset, we see that the new value for our bias is $18.91\text{ s} - 18\text{ s} = 0.91\text{ s}$. The remaining 0.91 s bias is influenced by the following factors, listed in order of decreasing magnitude: The filters used to isolate the signal and the station’s z-count time alignment with GPS time (order of hundreds of milliseconds), the processing delay at the receiver level (order of milliseconds), the transmission delay and the propagation delay over the channel from the station to the receiver (order of microseconds).

Further results from Jammertest 2025 in a GNSS-denied environment will be presented in the full paper, together with an extended description of R-Mode message 55. This message mitigates reference-station timing biases, removing a large portion of the observed error. The remaining biases will be reduced through improved control of the processing chain, including the filtering stages and the computation time, potentially lowering the timing bias to a few microseconds to hundreds of nanoseconds.

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ENLITOR: A Passive Acoustic Multi-Sensor Network for Enhanced Situational Awareness in Maritime Infrastructure Protection

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Abstract — *The protection of maritime offshore infrastructure is of increasing strategic importance due to the growing reliance on subsea assets such as energy installations, communication cables, and pipelines. This paper presents ENLITOR, a passive acoustic seabed-deployed multi-sensor network designed to enhance situational awareness in complex maritime environments. The system integrates distributed hydroacoustic sensing with modern data processing and communication frameworks to detect, classify, and track both surface and subsurface targets. In addition to passive monitoring, ENLITOR can be complemented by active imaging techniques and auxiliary sensor modalities, enabling a comprehensive and scalable surveillance solution. The paper outlines the system architecture, key functionalities, and results from initial technology testing, demonstrating its effectiveness for long-term, wide-area monitoring of critical infrastructure.*

Keywords — *situational awareness, multi-sensor networks, active imaging, sensors and instruments, technology testing, underwater acoustics, maritime security*

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime offshore infrastructure, including offshore wind farms, subsea cables, pipelines, and naval installations, represents critical assets that are increasingly exposed to both accidental and intentional threats [1]. Ensuring persistent situational awareness in such environments is challenging due to limited visibility, harsh environmental conditions, and the vast spatial extent of monitored areas.

Traditional surveillance approaches often rely on mobile platforms or localized sensing systems, which may lack persistence or scalability. In contrast, distributed seabed-deployed systems offer continuous monitoring capabilities and improved spatial coverage. Passive acoustic sensing, in particular, provides a stealthy and energy-efficient means of detecting maritime activity over long distances [2].

This paper introduces ENLITOR, a passive acoustic multi-sensor network designed to provide persistent situational awareness for maritime infrastructure protection. The system combines hydroacoustic sensing with advanced processing and integration capabilities, allowing for scalable deployment in diverse operational scenarios.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

ENLITOR is based on a modular, seabed-deployed architecture consisting of multiple underwater nodes interconnected via fiber-optic communication links to a centralized command unit. Each node is equipped with hydrophones and embedded processing capabilities, forming a distributed sensing network.

1) A. Multi-Sensor Network Design

The system operates as a multi-sensor network, where each node contributes to a shared situational picture. While passive acoustic sensing forms the core modality, the architecture allows integration of additional sensors and instruments, such as environmental sensors or active acoustic components.

The distributed design enables:

- Wide-area coverage through spatially separated nodes
- Redundancy and robustness against node failure
- Cooperative detection and tracking through data fusion

2) B. Data Processing and Communication

Data acquired at the sensor nodes is either pre-processed locally or transmitted to the central command unit for further analysis. The system supports modern communication standards and open interfaces, enabling integration into existing command and control (C2) systems.

Advanced signal processing techniques, including spectral analysis (e.g., LOFAR/DEMON) and machine learning-based classification, are applied to identify and categorize acoustic signatures of vessels and underwater objects [4].

III. SITUATIONAL AWARENESS AND DETECTION CAPABILITIES

A key objective of ENLITOR is to enhance situational awareness by providing continuous, real-time information about maritime activity. The system supports multiple operational functions:

- **Detection** of surface vessels and submerged objects based on acoustic signatures
- **Tracking** of targets across multiple nodes using time-difference-of-arrival methods
- **Classification** of targets based on spectral and temporal features
- **Localization** of acoustic sources within the monitored area

The combination of distributed sensing and centralized data fusion enables a comprehensive understanding of the operational environment, even in complex acoustic conditions [3].

IV. INTEGRATION OF ACTIVE IMAGING AND AUXILIARY SENSORS

While ENLITOR primarily relies on passive acoustic sensing, it can be extended with active imaging capabilities to improve detection performance in specific scenarios. Active sonar components can be deployed selectively to provide high-resolution imaging of targets or areas of interest [5].

Furthermore, the system supports the integration of additional sensors and instruments, such as:

- Environmental sensors (e.g., temperature, salinity, sound velocity)
- Optical or electromagnetic sensors (where applicable)
- External data sources such as AIS for surface vessel identification

This multi-modal approach enhances detection reliability and reduces ambiguity in target classification.

V. TECHNOLOGY TESTING AND VALIDATION

Initial technology testing of the ENLITOR system has been conducted in representative maritime environments to evaluate its performance under realistic conditions. The testing focused on:

- Detection range and sensitivity of passive acoustic sensors
- Reliability of communication between nodes and command units
- Accuracy of target classification algorithms
- System robustness under varying environmental conditions

The results demonstrate that ENLITOR is capable of detecting and tracking maritime targets over significant distances, while maintaining stable operation over extended periods. The modular architecture allows iterative improvements and adaptation to specific deployment scenarios.

VI. DISCUSSION

The use of passive acoustic multi-sensor networks represents a promising approach for maritime infrastructure protection [6]. Compared to traditional surveillance systems, ENLITOR offers several advantages:

- Persistent, 24/7 monitoring without active emissions
- Scalability to large areas through distributed deployment
- Flexibility through integration of additional sensing modalities
- Compatibility with existing maritime security frameworks

However, challenges remain in areas such as data management, environmental variability, and system deployment logistics. Ongoing research focuses on improving machine learning models for acoustic classification and optimizing network configurations for different operational environments.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presented ENLITOR, a passive acoustic multi-sensor network designed to enhance situational awareness for maritime offshore infrastructure protection. By combining distributed sensing, advanced signal processing, and integration capabilities, the system provides a scalable and effective solution for long-term monitoring.

Future work will focus on further technology testing, integration of additional sensor modalities, and the development of advanced data fusion techniques to improve system performance in complex maritime environments.

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Multi-View Estimation of 3D Vessel Positions Using Scattering Transform

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Abstract—Accurate visual perception is critical for maritime monitoring; however, classical feature detection techniques (e.g., gradient-based detectors) are sensitive to environmental disturbances and challenging imaging conditions, such as long-range viewing, low-texture surfaces, and reflections, which limit their performance. Since 3D reconstruction accuracy depends on the quality of the extracted features, a feature representation that is robust to perturbations and invariant to transformations is desired. While deep learning approaches have demonstrated good performance in feature extraction, these methods often require large-scale annotated datasets for training, which are often scarce in the maritime domain and may generalize poorly, especially in challenging environmental conditions. The Wavelet Scattering Transform (WST) provides a feature representation that is stable to small deformations, invariant to affine transformations, and robust to geometric and photometric variations. While WST has shown remarkable stability in classification and recognition tasks, its use for robust feature detection and extraction in stereo and multi-view stereo for vessel localization remains largely underexplored. This work investigates the application of WST for feature detection, extraction, and sparse 3D reconstruction in a stereo and multi-view stereo setup. Experiments on simulated real-world maritime environments demonstrate that the proposed system enhances the stability of features, improves depth estimation, and consequently improves the spatial localization of vessels.

Index Terms—3D reconstruction, Wavelet Scattering Transform, Depth Estimation

I. INTRODUCTION

The maritime environment is a critical component of global trade, accounting for more than 80% of international commerce and supporting strategic functions such as fishing, naval operations, communications, and offshore energy [1]. Increases in vessel traffic, expansion of offshore infrastructure, and adverse environmental conditions such as fog, sea reflections, and dynamic lighting pose a significant challenge to maritime monitoring, making situational awareness essential for safe and resilient maritime operations. To address these challenges, visual analysis techniques from computer vision have been adopted.

In computer vision, features are distinct patterns, such as corners, used by algorithms to understand visual data, while feature representation is a structured numerical encoding of these patterns designed to capture relevant information [2]. Classical hand-crafted feature descriptors detect and describe structures present in images such as blobs, corners, and edges using predefined mathematical formulations typically based on gradient variations or local pixel intensity changes [3]. While

these classical feature detectors are efficient, they rely heavily on well-defined image structures [3], making them sensitive to noise and environmental disturbances, which are common in maritime scenes. In contrast, deep learning methods, on the other hand, learn feature representations directly from annotated datasets through optimization using gradient-based techniques. Although deep learning approaches are robust, they require large-scale annotated datasets, often limited in maritime domains [4].

WST-based representations bridge these gaps by providing feature representations that are stable, consistent, and meaningful even in challenging conditions. The WST network has an architecture similar to a deep neural network and works by analyzing image signals at different scales, capturing variations, and the resulting feature maps are smoothed to produce stable and informative features [5]. The existing literature has shown the effectiveness of WST in various tasks such as text classification, segmentation, and object recognition [6], and this work builds on these methods to achieve robust feature representations that are invariant to translation, geometric deformation, and stable to noise. The resulting features are then used in downstream tasks for feature matching and depth estimation to enable reliable estimation of the positions of ships under variable environmental conditions.

II. METHODS

The proposed pipeline extracts robust features from maritime images and performs depth estimation for vessel localization. Input images are preprocessed and passed through a WST network to generate multi-scale and multi-orientation feature maps. From these feature maps, the most informative areas in the images are highlighted while the less important are suppressed resulting in a saliency map. A sparse set of reliable keypoints is selected from the saliency map, and local patches around the keypoints are used as descriptors for feature matching. Feature correspondences are established based on a cost metric with outlier filtering. The proposed method is then evaluated against classical feature extractors to assess its robustness to scale variations, low contrast conditions, and its computational efficiency. Experiments are conducted under low-contrast scenarios (e.g., fog) and normal illuminations (e.g., sunny conditions). Both stereo and tri-stereo camera configurations are used, with cameras placed at various target

distances to evaluate the extent to which the tri-stereo setup improves reconstruction over the stereo configuration.

III. CONCLUSION

Experiments conducted on a simulated maritime environment with vessels placed at target distances of 60 meters, 130 meters, and 200 meters under normal illumination conditions show that the proposed WST-based method performed comparably with classical methods, in terms of number of features detected and spatial localization of vessels. In low visibility conditions, classical methods, struggle to detect keypoints beyond a target distance of 60 meters. In contrast, WST remained relatively stable over long-ranges even though the number of detected features and depth estimates precision decreased. Overall, the proposed WST-based feature detection approach demonstrates robustness and reliability in long-range maritime applications, particularly under low-contrast conditions.

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